

THE PECULIARITY OF PSYCHOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN OF PRE-SCHOOL AGE

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Abstract. *The article presents the results of research on the theories of the psychological development of a preschool child, the pedagogical requirements for the organization of the preschool educational process, factors affecting the personal development of the child. Furthermore, scientific and theoretical ideas on creating the perception of the environment in the process of preparing a child for school education were set out.*

Keywords: *psychological development, social life, social environment, activity, mental quality, ability, intellect, development, adaptation, environment, didactics, principle, motive, communication.*

Introduction. Several years of pedagogical experiences in the field of pedagogy and psychology have shown the need to take into account their age characteristics and mental development in the process of educating preschool children. The child's psychological age is determined by his place in the educational system and society. There are two main reasons for this. *First*, to pay attention to the fact that the child's age is related to the conditions of his development; *secondly*, age characteristic means not only the understanding of the development and mental aspects of the child at this stage, but also that mental qualities may have been formed in him. Emphasizing that education is at the forefront of mental development, the level of development, abilities and individuality of the child are taken into account at each age stage.

Analysis of literature on the topic. Not only the comprehensive adaptation of the child to social life, but also relying on this level lays the foundation for his future development. It is necessary to pay attention to the pedagogic-psychological conditions created in the pre-school educational institution for the child's development in the implementation of the main tasks of education at different age stages, as well as the compatibility of these conditions with communication and activities. The activity of the child is considered very important and has "universal" importance. In the process of activity, the child learns to use various objects and things, plans his actions, organizes his thoughts, and puts into practice the knowledge he has acquired. According to psychologists, the foundation for the formation of mental characteristics and abilities is created during early and preschool childhood.

Swiss psychologist Jean Piaget created a theory of child thinking based on logic and biology. Based on these ideas, it is concluded that the basis of mental development is the development of the intellect. The scientist proved in his experiments that speech affects the emergence of the first concept and the development of the mind. According to him, adaptation of the organism to the environment takes place in the process of development. In pedagogy, adaptation is considered the main process of transitioning students from one situation to another, from one activity in one environment to another, for example: we can take as an example the process of adapting a child to school [5]. It is known that the leading activity in preschool age is play. Play is a type of free activity, participation in which is determined according to the wishes

of the child. D. B. Elkonin expresses the opinion that the game is an action developed by children and represents work and social relations with children and adults [6,34-35].

As a solution to the problem of introducing preschool children to the environment, it is appropriate to use the above-mentioned ideas in the educational process.

According to Piaget, imagination and drawings exist neither in the subject nor in the object, but are the result of an active interaction between the subject and the object [5,195-196].

Pedagogical educators and parents should pay attention to the great role of the family in the formation of a child's personality. Children's ideas about the environment are formed not only in the family, but also in the preschool educational institution. Therefore, the content of pre-school education programs should be aimed at general development. Didactic principles and scientific knowledge should be reflected in this program. In the period of early infancy and childhood, the tasks of education appear the same when compared to each other. All the psychic abilities and characteristics listed above are subject to motives. Motive is the main reason that motivates a person to certain actions [2,94]. Under the influence of motives, voluntary behavior, exemplary forms of understanding are embodied in various activities of the child. For example: play activities, drawing, building games, etc. According to psychologists, new motives for communication arise in children during preschool age. It has personal and business motives. Personal communication motives are related to the internal problems that concern the child, and business motives are motives related to doing one or another job. These motives are gradually replaced by learning motives related to the acquisition of knowledge, skills and competences. These motives appear in place of children's natural curiosity, which begins in early childhood. Self-expression motives are also evident at this age [4,45].

Along with the formation of personal orientations in preschool childhood, the child learns to communicate, interacts with other people, develops social behavior and moral qualities. All the mentioned points help to determine the directions of preschool education. Cognitive processes, namely perception, visual thinking and imagination, develop rapidly during preschool childhood. The age period of such development is unrepeatable. In elementary school, the child's logical thinking develops further.

According to L.S. Vygotsky, the child's feelings and sensitivity are very strong during the preschool period [3]. The main way to influence preschool children is to enrich the types of activities and to be able to choose and use the most effective and convenient methods. Also, the most important aspect of achieving success in preschool education is the systematic organization of activities.

It is necessary to increase the content of preparing children for school in preschool education. School changes the child's place in social relations. It is necessary to convey to the child that a serious approach to study is one of the demands of the society and to teach him to voluntarily control his behavior. When preparing children for school, cognitive activity and logical thinking should be developed. In the timely preparation of preschool children for school education, it is necessary to form the necessary knowledge, skills and qualifications, which will create the qualities that students need to master. In order to organize psychological readiness for school, it is necessary to develop personal qualities in the child, mentally prepare for the processes that occur in school education, new conditions.

Results. The performed tasks ensure the development of mental characteristics and abilities in the child, for example: the need for communication; speech development; proper use

of items; organic development of perception and thinking; such as the child being able to distinguish himself from others. However, these features do not determine the future "characteristics", but will be of particular importance in the further development of the child. A child does not have his inner world during his early years. It is necessary to implement the following pedagogical requirements when organizing the preschool education process: 1. Ability to incorporate games, subject-based and creative activities into the teaching content, and correctly choose the training methodology; 2. Introducing children to natural phenomena and community life, developing their speech, organizing using game elements and creative tasks; 3. Taking into account the fact that the lessons consist of the child's independent activities, enriching with the necessary knowledge and skills while playing, organizing drawing and building games.

The educational process implemented in pre-school education, along with the formation of children's ideas about the environment, should also include the skills to take their place in this environment. The pre-school period is a flexible period in the child's psyche, and if pedagogical and psychological processes are organized correctly, the quality indicator shows a high result. However, attention should be paid to the individual changes of each child. This guarantees an increase in the quality of education.

So, based on the above considerations, it should be noted that effective education is the driving force of a child's mental development. Development and education are different processes, while being proportional to each other. Development is a process with self-moving internal laws. And education is a social need to acquire knowledge and education in the process of developing historically relevant characteristics for a person.

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